

Research Science and
Innovation House

XXI ASRDA INNOVATION TECHNOLOGIYALAR, FAN VA TA'LIM TARAQQIYOTIDAGI DOLZARB MUAMMOLAR" konferensiyasida

Abduraxmanova Zilola Yoqubjon qizi

TEACHING DISCUSSION IN THE READING CLASS
mavzusi uchun

DIPLOM

bilan taqdirlanadi

Eshkaraev

BOSH MUHARRIR:
ESHKARAEV.S.CH

SERTIFIKAT

Abduraxmanova Zilola Yoqubjon qizi

MAVZU: TEACHING DISCUSSION IN THE READING CLASS

"XXI ASRDA INNOVATSION TEXNOLOGIYALAR, FAN VA TA'LIM
TARAQQIYOTIDAGI DOLZARB MUAMMOLAR" nomli
konferensiyaning 2025-yil 12 - sonida nashr etildi. Ushbu maqola
tahrir hay'atidan o'tkazilib, ijobiiy baholandi va jurnalga nashr etish
uchun tavsiya etildi.

19.12.2025

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Erkaboyeva Sarvinoz

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nomli maqola "XXI asrda innovatsion texnologiyalar, fan va ta'lim taraqqiyotidagi dolzarb muammolar" nomli konferensiyasi tahrir hay'atidan o'tganligi bo'yicha

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Maqola mualliflari: Abduraxmanova Zilola Yoqubjon qizi, Erkaboyeva Sarvinoz

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A handwritten signature in blue ink, likely belonging to the editor-in-chief.

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